

Free and Open-Source Software Solutions in the GeoRondônia Project: Efficiency in Georeferencing of Rural Settlements with QGIS and GeoINCRA plugin

Ranieli dos Anjos de Souza ¹, Valdir Moura ¹, Bárbara Laura Tavares ¹, Marcelo Vinicius Assis de Brito ¹, Tiago Prudencio Silvano ¹, Leandro França ^{2,3}

¹ GREES/IFRO, Space Research Group of the Federal Institute of Rondônia, campus Colorado do Oeste, BR 435, Km 63, 79993-000 – Colorado do Oeste, RO – Brazil – (ranieli.anjos, valdir.moura@ifro.edu.br, (barbaralauratavares, marcelobrito03, tiagoprudencio16@gmail.com

² GeoOne Innovation and Training, Walfredo M. Brandao Street, 58052-200 – João Pessoa, PB – Brazil – geoleandro.franca@gmail.com

³ IFPB, Federal Institute of Paraíba, Campus Picuí, Rodovia PB-151, s/n, 58187-000 - Picuí, PB – Brazil – leandro.franca@ifpb.edu.br

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Abstract

Georeferencing is much more than just registering properties or objects in a known cartographic system. In Brazil, it is a fundamental piece for the registration of properties above 25 hectares at a registry office and for definitive titling by the regulatory body, which is INCRA. When executing georeferencing projects with a large set of data, such as in rural settlements, the big challenge is the time for collection, processing, assembly of parts and certification in the Land Management System (SIGEF). And for this, the Open-Source of Geographic Information System can be an indispensable partner in land regularization programs, such as the GeoRondônia Project (INCRA/IFRO), which is being implemented in more than 100 settlements and more than 25,000 rural lots in the state from Rondônia. Such dynamics of processing georeferenced data, in a more automated and massive way, has not been found even in commercial software. Therefore, in this study, we will show how this is possible using a well-structured workflow and plugins based on free software and code open (FOSS). This article presents the productivity gains achieved by the GeoRondônia project, which uses QGIS functionalities and GeoINCRA plugin to automate tasks. We implemented a flow capable of detecting topological errors in the database, defining confrontations semi-automatically, and filling out the .ods spreadsheet (certification document) in bulk. All of this brought a gain in quality and time to the project, and can be replicated in any demand with a greater volume of data.

1. Introduction

The National Institute of Colonization and Agrarian Reform (INCRA) is a body of the Brazilian federal government, linked to the Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Supply (MAPA). Its main mission is to execute national agrarian policy, promoting agrarian reform and land planning in Brazil. INCRA works on several fronts to guarantee land regularization, sustainable development and social justice in the countryside.

The Amazon is a strategic region for INCRA due to its unique characteristics and specific challenges. The body works on land regularization to guarantee the legal security of squatters and combat land grabbing, thus contributing to environmental preservation (Reis, 2023). Regularization facilitates the control and monitoring of rural properties, helping to combat illegal deforestation and environmental degradation (Cunha, 2021). Furthermore, INCRA promotes settlement projects that seek sustainable development, integrating agricultural production with environmental conservation through agroecology and sustainable management practices (Le Tourneau and Bursztyn, 2010).

INCRA also plays an important role in social inclusion, promoting agrarian reform and land regularization, which improves the living conditions of thousands of rural families in the Amazon. This guarantees access to basic services and public policies, contributing to the socioeconomic development of the region (Menezes, 2020).

For regularization to become a reality, INCRA has signed Decentralized Execution Terms in several Brazilian states. In Rondônia, the partnership was established with the Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Rondônia (IFRO), through TED 20/2021/INCRA-SEDE/IFRO, called GeoRondônia Project. The project aims to serve and document more than 25,000 families and rural properties. To achieve this, the necessary steps are the georeferencing of properties, rural environmental registration and occupational supervision.

The biggest challenge of the project is time and qualified labor, therefore, aiming to increase productivity, the Free and Open-Source Software Solution was developed, called FOSSS GeoRondônia, which integrates features from QGIS and, mainly, the GeoINCRA Plugin. This set

of functions enabled temporal gains, professional qualification of employees and finances, as it is completely free, and can be replicated to any other large data volume project involving georeferencing.

The georeferencing of rural properties is a complex process that requires knowledge in surveying, legal aspects, precision and efficiency. With the growing demand for land regularization in Brazil, especially in large areas such as the Amazon, it is essential to seek solutions that reduce costs, automate tasks and ensure data quality. This article presents the productivity gains achieved by the GeoRondônia project, which uses QGIS and the GeoINCRA plugin to automate tasks for property georeferencing certification. The methodology developed involves data validation and quality control, with automation implemented in Python, ensuring accuracy in property certification and large-scale generation of .ods spreadsheets (certification document).

2. GeoRondônia Project Work Methodology

The GeoRondônia Project is made up of 3 main goals: Occupational Supervision (for around 25,000 families), the Rural Environmental Registry (for around 25,000

rural properties) and the Georeferencing of properties belonging to the settlements included in the TED (for more than 31,000 km), the latter being the most complex step and most necessary for INCRA to regularize properties (Figure 1).

Initially, all georeferenced data processing dynamics were carried out manually, which required a lot of labor and time. Therefore, the Space Research Group (GREES), from the Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Rondônia (IFRO), together with other collaborators from the Paraíba Institute (IFPB), has supported the project's actions for the development of innovative technology, in order to optimize actions involving the certification of rural properties, through free tools.

From this joint effort, the Free and Open-Source Software Solution GeoRondônia (called FOSSS GeoRondônia) emerged, making it possible to automate the processes and bring not only a temporal gain, but also a qualitative one in the elaboration of the parts of the georeferencing, which before being inserted into INCRA's Land Management System (SIGEF), goes through stages of collection, processing, organization and validation.

Figure 1. Location of rural settlements in Rondônia. Source: (INCRA, 2024).

The georeferenced data processing flow generates spreadsheets in the .ods format, required by INCRA, with information on the limits, location and name of the properties, as shown in Figure 2.

Once the database has been assembled, after being pre-processed to meet the precision required by INCRA's Georeferencing Technical Manual, the next step is to generate the spreadsheets in an automated way, and launch them in SIGEF.

This is an innovative methodology, unavailable in any other Geographic Information System, open or private, whose steps were developed to meet the highest technical quality standards for georeferencing projects with large

volumes of data, such as in GeoRondônia, which has worked in settlements that have more than 2,000 properties, and can be replicated to other states and projects.

To optimize demands, the main steps of FOSSS GeoRondônia after adjusting the observations tracked in the field, to meet positional accuracies, are: a) elimination of topological errors in the geometries of the settlement database; b) elimination of errors when filling in vertices and limits in the settlement database; c) elimination of errors in the name of the property and .ods spreadsheet; d) generation of .ods spreadsheets and entry into SIGEF.

Figure 2. Georeferenced data processing flow.

2.1. GNSS Data Collection and Settlement Base Correction

The first stage involves the collection of highly accurate GNSS points in the field, by teams from the GeoRondônia project. This data is essential for correcting INCRA's Rural Settlements base, whose precision of the collected points guarantees the reliability of the geospatial information used in georeferencing.

Georeferencing is a product that can be questioned at any time, as there are overlapping problems with neighboring lots. As a result, the methodology adopted by the technician responsible for the GeoRondônia Project is to collect first order points in the SIRGAS2000 Geodetic Reference System, with tracking for around 30 minutes, using a local base, post-processing with the Brazilian Monitoring Network Continuous (RBMC) from Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE), using the static method, which guarantees greater data reliability over all other collection methods, and positional accuracy better than or equal to 0.50 m, for vertices located on

artificial limits, as is the case with the boundaries of rural properties.

2.2. Validation of Geospatial Data in QGIS

After collecting and post-processing the vertices, the database called GeoRural is built, in which the vertices, limits and parcels are inserted (Figure 3), and then the georeferenced data is validated in QGIS. The GeoRondônia project developed routines in Python that are integrated with QGIS to check data consistency and accuracy. This step is essential to identify and correct topological errors (overlap, gap, lack of connectivity, etc.), ensuring that the data is ready for certification.

For this, features of the LF Tools plugin (França et al., 2021) are used to evaluate the polygons that overlap (Figure 4A), then a vector file is generated that indicates the location of the error, using the Polygon Overlay tool. In the case of gaps, that is, lots that are not connected, they are evaluated using the QGIS Dissolve tool, which generates a file indicating the location to be corrected (Figure 4B).

Finally, and one of the most important, is the connectivity check, to analyze whether all lots have corresponding vertices, or whether there are more vertices than indicated

for the lot, using the Extract Vertices and Select by Location tool in QGIS. The result is a file with a selection of all vertices that have correct validation (Figure 4C).

Figure 3. GeoRural database.

Figure 4. Example of topological correction in FOSSS GeoRondônia.

2.3. Task Automation with the GeoINCRA Plugin

The GeoINCRA plugin, developed to optimize the georeferencing process in accordance with INCRA standards, plays a fundamental role in automating tasks. The plugin's main features include:

- Feed Vertex Layer: loads point features to the vertices layer.
- Download SIGEF ODS Spreadsheet: generates an empty .ods spreadsheet for later filling.
- Consult INCRA Database: connects to the INCRA database to generate vector layers.
- INCRA CSV to PointZ Layer: transforms .csv files into PointZ layers.
- GeoRural for TopoGeo: copies features to the TopoGeo database, facilitating the generation of descriptive memorials and topographic plans.

- Generate TXT for ODS spreadsheet: creates text files to fill in the SIGEF .ods spreadsheet.
- Fill Vertex Code: automates the filling of vertex codes.
- GeoRural for ODS spreadsheet: automatically generates .ods spreadsheet, based on the features created in the database.

The GeoINCRA plugin is a tool developed in Python language for the QGIS software, through the basic structure and logic of the processing framework. The objective of the plugin is to directly query SIGEF data, load the data into the database GeoRural, automate the filling of attributes and, mainly, generate the data necessary to complete the Certification spreadsheet (SILVANO et al, 2022). The total Python routine is available on public GitHub (<https://github.com/OpenGeoOne/GeoINCRA>) and can be updated by the user community, according to demand. Table 1 presents the main features of the plugin.

Table 1. Main features of the GeoINCRA plugin.

Tool	Functionality	Parameters
Feed Vertex layer**	Feed vertex layer from GeoRural database.	Point layer; vertex layer; (GeoRural); precision X: precision Y; Z precision; positioning method; vertex code; Vertex type; Qrcode
Download SIGEF ODS Spreadsheet**	Generates an empty .ods spreadsheet for filling	Directory to save spreadsheet
Consult INCRA Base*	Connects to the INCRA database to generate vector layers.	Area of interest; type of land collection layer; directory to save result.
INCRA CSV for PointZ Layer*	Transforms .csv files into PointZ layers.	File directory (*.csv); directory to save point layer.
GeoRural to TopoGeo**	Copies features from the GeoRural database to the TopoGeo database.	Vertex layer (GeoRural); limit points (TopoGeo); Boundary layer (GeoRural); confrontation (TopoGeo), parcel layer (GeoRural), property area (topoGeo).
Generate TXT for ODS Spreadsheet**	Creates text file to fill in the SIGEF .ods spreadsheet.	Vertex layer (GeoRural), boundary layer (GeoRural), parcel layer (GeoRural); directory to save file (*.txt).
GeoRural for ODS spreadsheet*	Generates .ods spreadsheet, filled from the features created in the database.	Vertex layer (GeoRural), boundary layer (GeoRural), parcel layer (GeoRural); directory to save spreadsheet

Mandatory parameters*

Optional parameters**

2.4. Automatic Generation of ODS Spreadsheets

One of the major innovations of the project is the automatic generation of .ods spreadsheets for hundreds of properties. Using layers stored in GeoPackage files (.gpkg) and the GeoINCRA plugin tools in QGIS, the project can generate these spreadsheets in a massive way. This significantly reduces the time required for preparation, increasing productivity and eliminating human errors.

The GeoINCRA plugin was developed for projects involving a single property, or properties with multiple parts. But it has been updated to meet massive demands, in order to enable the generation of georeferencing products in an efficient and practical way.

In Figure 5, a complete project for a property can be seen, involving the vertices, limits and plot layers of a single rural property, using the GeoINCRA plugin. In Figure 6, it is possible to observe the development of a project with several properties, using the functionalities of QGIS, LF Tools and GeoINCRA plugins to generate these layers with precision and practicality.

Considering that the GeoRondônia Project needs to generate more than 25,000 spreadsheets in an accurate and efficient way, the FOSSS GeoRondônia is a functionality that meets the principle of efficiency in public administration, which aims to offer the best service with good use of the invested resource.

Figure 5. Example of a single rural property database using the GeoINCRA plugin.

Figure 6. Example of a database of 42 rural properties using FOSSS GeoRondônia.

3. Results and Benefits

The processing of georeferenced data on a very high scale, using this new solution, allowed the generation of products with precision and the consequent launch in SIGEF with reliability, which can be replicated for any project in Brazil. This has promoted greater efficiency in the services performed, and helped INCRA in meeting the large volume of Agrarian Reform demands.

The results obtained with FOSS GeoRondônia are remarkable:

- Process Automation: assembling the database with greater security, precision and practicality.
- Automation in product generation: .ods spreadsheets that were previously created manually are now generated automatically.
- Time Reduction: spreadsheet preparation time was reduced by 70%.

- Error Elimination: topological and writing errors have been eliminated, ensuring accurate and consistent data.
- Cost Savings: using QGIS and the GeoINCRA plugin eliminates the need for expensive licenses, allowing for a more efficient allocation of public resources.

Currently, we have already organized the databases of 10 Settlement Projects using FOSS GeoRondônia, which total around 2 thousand properties. A very productive result was the field collection, processing and launch of 3 new Settlements (574 properties) in the state of Rondônia in record time, for launch by the Federal Government, all carried out between April and May 2024.

Before FOSS GeoRondônia, filling out the identification and perimeter tab was done manually, starting to fill in the coordinates from the northernmost point (Figure 7, left). With FOSS, after setting up the database in GeoRural, the GeoINCRA Plugin fills in all the data automatically (Figure 7, right).

Figure 7. ODS spreadsheet for SIGEF/INCRA.

Teixeira and Leite (2022) highlight that deforestation grew by 50% in non-designated forest areas. However, much of the information is generated based on the Rural Environmental Registry (CAR), a self-declaratory land use document, which is still unreliable, as there are considerable registration errors with overlapping in sustainable use conservation units and indigenous lands.

This highlights the importance of regularizing settlement projects to advance forest protection, thus, it is possible to correctly identify the occupants of these properties, consequently, the problems can be held responsible, in addition, the CAR can be done reliably and with georeferenced data. The GeoRondônia project, through the tools developed, such as the FOSS presented here, will contribute to meeting this urgent demand, which has been going on for decades.

4. Conclusion

The use of QGIS and the GeoINCRA plugin in the GeoRondônia project demonstrates how the adoption of FOSS can transform georeferencing projects. By automating tasks, reducing costs and ensuring data quality, these solutions significantly contribute to land regularization, environmental sustainability and socioeconomic development in the region. The methodology developed can be replicated in other Brazilian states, expanding the benefits throughout the country.

This represents a new story for Agrarian Reform in the state of Rondônia, and the resumption of INCRA's strength for actions that had been stopped for many years. The agility and quality of the work carried out by the GeoRondônia project using FOSS has restored the trust of the public involved. The development of FOSS

GeoRondônia brings many gains to the organization, at a regional and national level.

The advancement of the regularization of rural properties, which requires georeferencing and Rural Environmental Registration so that the definitive document can be issued by INCRA, is an action that reinforces environmental policy in Brazil.

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